

INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP IN ASEAN COUNTRIES: INSIGHTS FROM A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF CONTEMPORARY PRACTICES

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Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received: 22 Sept 2024 Revised: 5 Oct 2024 Accepted: 20 Oct 2024 Published: 1 Nov 2024</p>	<p>In this era of rapid changes of education environment, it is essential for the principals to apply instructional leadership to improve the school effectiveness by guiding the school teachers and students. This systematic review analyses 16 recent studies on instructional leadership in ASEAN educational settings. It emphasizes the crucial role of instructional leadership in improving teacher development, organizational commitment, and student outcomes. The research covers various contexts, including primary and vocational schools in countries such as Malaysia, Indonesia, and Singapore. Key findings show that effective instructional leadership significantly influences teacher professional growth, school climate, and student achievement. The studies reveal intricate relationships between leadership practices and educational outcomes, often influenced by factors like teacher self-efficacy and school health. Key themes include adapting leadership strategies to technological advancements and unprecedented challenges like the COVID-19 pandemic. The review also identifies variations in leadership perceptions and practices based on demographic factors. While consistently emphasizing the importance of instructional leadership, the research underscores the necessity of context-sensitive approaches. This comprehensive analysis provides valuable insights for educational policymakers and administrators, highlighting the critical role of instructional leadership in advancing educational quality and preparing students for future challenges.</p>
<p>Keywords: Instructional leadership, principal, systematic literature review, school effectiveness, ASEAN education</p> <p></p>	

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INTRODUCTION

Principals play a key role in enhancing teaching and learning outcomes in schools through instructional leadership. This method goes beyond typical management duties by concentrating on how principals guide, assist, and mentor teachers to boost student performance (Nguyen et al., 2022). By emphasizing teaching quality and academic success, instructional leadership shifts the principal's attention from administrative tasks to actively influencing the educational environment and cultivating a culture of ongoing improvement (Aureada, 2021).

For effective instructional leadership, principals must have a thorough understanding of effective teaching practices, curriculum design, and evaluation strategies (Li et al., 2023). They work with teachers to set high academic expectations, apply research-driven teaching methods, and use data to guide teaching practices. Key strategies include offering professional development opportunities, observing classrooms, and providing feedback to improve teaching quality (Kilag & Sasan, 2023). This active engagement positions principals as instructional leaders who directly impact classroom instruction and student success.

While the core principles of instructional leadership may be universally accepted, their implementation often varies depending on the local educational context, policies, and cultural dynamics. For instance, instructional leadership in countries with more decentralized educational systems may emphasize teacher autonomy, while in centralized systems, principals may have more prescriptive roles in implementing national curricula and policies (Kwan, 2016). The variation in how instructional leadership is enacted across different regions and schools invites comparisons of best practices, as well as an examination of the contextual factors that shape its effectiveness. These comparative aspects are essential to understanding how instructional leadership can be adapted and tailored to different educational environments, particularly in diverse regions such as ASEAN countries.

However, the role of principals as instructional leaders is not without challenges. In practice, principals must navigate a range of issues that complicate their ability to focus solely on instructional leadership. These challenges include addressing student mental health and well-being (Adelman & Taylor, 2014), ensuring school safety and a positive climate (Thapa et al., 2013), managing teacher recruitment and retention (Sutcher et al., 2019), and dealing with administrative burdens that detract from instructional leadership responsibilities. In many schools, especially those in under-resourced or high-need areas, principals face the dilemma of balancing their instructional leadership duties with urgent operational concerns. Moreover, as schools increasingly face complex challenges such as rapid technological change, socio-economic disparities, and diverse student needs, principals must adapt their leadership styles to ensure that all students receive a high-quality education and are prepared for future success (Kwan, 2016).

Effective instructional leadership thus involves not only the ability to influence teaching practices but also the capacity to manage and mitigate these emerging challenges. By creating a cohesive learning environment and fostering collaboration among staff members, principals can promote a shared sense of responsibility for student achievement, even amidst adversity (Chang et al., 2022). As such, exploring the variations in instructional leadership practices and addressing the challenges principals face are essential for understanding how to enhance both teaching quality and student outcomes in different educational contexts.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Instructional leadership is a crucial concept in educational administration, focusing on the role of school leaders in improving teaching and learning outcomes. While there are varying definitions, most researchers agree that instructional leadership involves actions taken by principals to promote student learning and enhance instructional quality. Hallinger and Murphy (1985) important work outlined three dimensions of instructional leadership: defining the school mission, managing the instructional program, and promoting a positive school learning climate. This framework has significantly influenced subsequent research and practice. More recent scholars have built upon this concept. As the field evolves, researchers continue to refine the definition and explore best practices in instructional leadership, emphasizing its crucial role in school improvement and student achievement.

Effective instructional leadership has been linked to improved student outcomes. Leaders who effectively communicate learning objectives, cultivate ongoing professional development, and utilize data-informed decision-making create environments conducive to both teacher and student success (Harris, 2014). Research consistently demonstrates that strong instructional leadership has a positive impact on student achievement, teacher satisfaction, and overall school performance (Robinson et al., 2008).

The impact of instructional leadership on improving student outcomes is a central focus of research. The previous studies highlighted various key themes that been researched together with instructional leadership. Cultural contextualization has become a crucial focus in recent instructional leadership research in ASEAN countries (Nguyen et al., 2023). Also, the integration of technology in education, particularly in the wake of the development of information and technology, has become a central concern for instructional leaders (Tran et al., 2020).

In a meta-analysis spanning from 2012 to 2021 on Asian countries, (Ikram et al., 2021) confirmed the positive effect of instructional leadership on student achievement and outcome. However, the highlighted the variability of this relationship based on contextual factors such as school size, socioeconomic status, and cultural norms. Addressing these findings, Hallinger and Liu (2023) proposed a context-sensitive model of instructional leadership tailored to ASEAN countries, underscoring the importance of adapting leadership practices to local cultural and institutional contexts. With the rapid changes happening on education environment, it is crucial to investigate the latest studies, in more focused educational settings. Therefore, this current study is aimed to investigate the key themes of best instructional leadership practices been implemented in ASEAN countries which will contribute towards school effectiveness and student outcome. Data were derived from Scopus and WoS database.

METHODOLOGY

A systematic literature review involving series of process such as identification, screening, checking eligibility, data abstraction and analysis and quality of assessment been involved in this study.

Identification

The systematic review process has two main stages for identifying appropriate publications for a report. The first stage is identifying keywords and related terms by consulting thesaurus, dictionaries, encyclopedias, and prior study. Following that, search strings are created for the Scopus and Web of Science databases (as shown in Table 1). During the first step of the systematic evaluation process, 2293 publications were found from both databases.

Table 1 : The search string.

Scopus	TITLE-ABS-KEY (instructional AND leadership AND in AND education) AND PUBYEAR > 2020 AND PUBYEAR < 2025 AND (LIMIT-TO (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Malaysia") OR LIMIT-TO (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Indonesia") OR LIMIT-TO (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Philippines") OR LIMIT-TO (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Thailand") OR LIMIT-TO (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Singapore") OR LIMIT-TO (AFFILCOUNTRY, "Brunei Darussalam"))
WoS	TS=principal instructional leadership in education (All Fields) and 2024 or 2023 or 2022 or 2021 (Publication Years) and Article (Document Types) and Article (Document Types) and English (Languages) and MALAYSIA or INDONESIA or THAILAND or VIETNAM or SINGAPORE or PHILIPPINES (Countries/Regions) and Article (Document Types) and All Open Access (Open Access)

Screening

During the screening phase, a wide range of possibly relevant research materials were analysed to locate content that

addressed the research questions. Specific criteria, such as the principal's instructional leadership in education, were employed to steer this phase. The initial screening rejected 593 publications. In the following step, 80 papers were reviewed based on the various exclusion and inclusion criteria outlined in Table 2. The emphasis was on reviewing literature (research papers) to make practical recommendations. This includes reviews, meta-synthesis, meta-analysis, books, book collections, chapters, and conference proceedings that had not been addressed in the most recent study. Only English-language publications were evaluated, and the search was limited to items published between 2021 and 2024. Furthermore, the screening procedure was limited to ASEAN countries, such as Malaysia, Indonesia, Singapore, Thailand, Brunei, Vietnam, and the Philippines.

Table 2: The selection criterion in searching

Criterion	Inclusion	Exclusion
Language	English	Non-English
Time line	Between 2021-2024	< 2021
Literature type	Journal (Article)	Conference, Book, Review
Publication Stage	Final	In Press
Subject Area	Education	Besides Education
Countries	ASEAN	Besides ASEAN

Eligibility

In the eligibility phase, which is the third step of the research process, the articles been carefully reviewed. The team of experts conducted a thorough analysis of all the titles and key content of each article to ensure they met the inclusion criteria and aligned with the research objectives. Unfortunately, 60 reports were found to be irrelevant and promptly discarded them. These articles had insignificant titles, included abstracts that were not related to the study's objectives, or were articles without full-text access backed by empirical evidence. Duplicate papers been removed as well, only finding, and rejecting 4 publications due to duplication. With unwavering focus and attention to detail, the remaining 16 articles been scrutinized, which were the only ones that met the criteria (refer to Figure 2).

Data Abstraction and Analysis

In this study, an integrative analysis approach was used to assess the role of instructional leadership in educational settings in ASEAN countries. The analysis involved examining and combining various research designs using quantitative methods to identify relevant topics and subtopics. Initially, 16 publications were analysed thoroughly to extract pertinent information. The significant studies related to instructional leadership in educational settings in ASEAN countries were then evaluated in terms of their methodology and research results. The authors collaborated with other co-authors to develop themes based on the evidence gathered in the study. Throughout the data analysis process, a log was kept to record relevant analyses. To ensure consistency in the theme design process, the authors meticulously compared the results and discussed any discrepancies, reflecting a thorough, rigorous, and collaborative approach.

Quality of assessment / Appraisal of Quality

The themes that were generated were adjusted to ensure consistency. Two professionals in education management and administration fields conducted an analysis to confirm the validity of the issues. An expert review phase was then carried out to establish the domain validity of each subtheme, ensuring clarity, importance, and appropriateness. Each article was evaluated based on quality criteria such as clear research aims, relevant research methods and design, appropriate recruitment strategy, data collection, data analysis, clear statement of findings, and the research's value. Lastly, all 16 articles were reviewed after quality evaluation. Figure 1 below shows the Flow diagram of the proposed searching study.

Figure 1 below shows the Flow diagram of the proposed searching study.

RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

The practice of instructional leadership is crucial for improving educational outcomes and supporting teacher development. Various studies have emphasized its significance in different educational settings. Collectively, these studies confirm that effective instructional leadership plays a crucial role in enhancing teacher professional development, fostering organizational commitment, and contributing to the overall success of educational institutions. Across different methodologies and contexts, the research highlights the wide-ranging advantages of strong instructional leadership in schools. There are some themes and sub themes been identified in these articles such as principal’s instructional leadership role with teacher professional development (Nguyen et al., 2023), organizational commitment (Sukarmin & Sin, 2022) and teacher’s self-efficacy (Siriparp et al., 2022), school environment (Fred & Singh, 2021) and innovation (Maisyaroh et al., 2024).

Principal Instructional Leadership and Teachers

Instructional leadership is critical in creating a climate that encourages teacher professional development, increases organisational commitment, and raises self-efficacy, all of which are essential components for educational institution success. Professional development under the supervision of instructional leaders frequently includes specialised training sessions, mentoring, and chances for teachers to take on leadership responsibilities that directly contribute to their growth and performance in the classroom (Bush & Glover, 2020). This type of leadership promotes a culture of continual learning and improvement, which is critical for

adjusting to educational advances and difficulties. Effective leaders inspire commitment by expressing support for teacher efforts, establishing a common vision, and efficiently managing resources to achieve school objectives (Hallinger & Heck, 2010). This dedication is critical to the stability and success of educational organisations because it increases teacher retention and overall job happiness. Leaders who provide supportive and constructive feedback, promote collaborative practices, and foster an empowering environment increase instructors' confidence in their instructional abilities (Tschannen-Moran & Barr, 2004). Teachers with high self-efficacy are more likely to use dynamic and effective teaching approaches, which leads to improved student outcomes. Instructional leaders who prioritise professional development, organisational commitment, and teacher self-efficacy improve not only individual teacher performance but also school-wide success, ultimately influencing student achievement and institutional goals (Leithwood, et al., 2008). Following is the findings of the influence of instructional leadership according to the subthemes.

Influence on Teacher Professional Development (Amzat et al., 2022): Research consistently shows that the instructional leadership of principals significantly contributes to promoting teacher professional development. Principals who actively engage in instructional practices and provide clear guidance and support create a culture of continuous learning and improvement among teachers. This, in turn, enhances the overall quality of education delivered (Nguyen et al., 2023).

Impact on Organizational Commitment (Awang et al., 2022): Effective instructional leadership has a positive impact on teachers' organizational commitment. Leaders who show a strong dedication to instructional excellence and cultivate a supportive, inclusive school environment contribute to building a sense of loyalty and dedication among teachers. This commitment is essential for the long-term success and stability of educational institutions.

Role in Teacher Self-Efficacy (Thien & Liu, 2024): Instructional leadership significantly impacts teacher self-efficacy. Principals can enhance teacher confidence by providing resources, professional development, and constructive feedback. Table 3 summarize the articles which is related to the theme's principal instructional leadership and teachers.

Table 3: Summary of Instructional Leadership and Teachers

Author(s)	Title	Year	Methodology	Findings
Rahman et al.	TACIT Knowledge in Instructional Leadership: Evidence from Malaysian Secondary Principals	2022	Survey of 202 secondary principals	Principals have a broad knowledge of instructional leadership. Significant variances exist depending on leadership experience and age.
Amzat et al.	Estimating the Effect of Principal Instructional and Distributed Leadership on Professional Development of Teachers in Jakarta, Indonesia	2022	Quantitative study with 430 participants, using stratified sampling and analysed with SEM through SmartPLS	The direct impact of both instructional and distributed leadership on teacher professional development. Instructional leadership directly affects distributed leadership.

Nguyen et al.	Principal instructional leadership and its influence on teachers' professional development at Vietnamese primary schools	2023	Qualitative study with in-depth interviews of 12 principals and 24 teachers from 12 schools across four provinces	Singaporean school leaders used a selective instructional leadership method. Instructional leadership strategies that prioritise professional development and a pleasant school atmosphere were substantially linked to teacher competencies.
Nguyen et al.	Exploring the relationships between instructional leadership and teacher competences: Singapore primary school teachers' perceptions	2022	Survey of 224 key personnel and 462 teachers from 28 Singapore primary schools	Singaporean school leaders used a selective instructional leadership method. Instructional leadership strategies that prioritise professional development and a pleasant school atmosphere were substantially linked to teacher competencies.
Sukarmin & Sin	The Influence of Principal Instructional Leadership Behaviour On The Organisational Commitment Of Junior High School Teachers In Surakarta	2022	Quantitative cross-sectional survey (264 teachers), analysed using SPSS and SmartPLS	Moderate principle instructional leadership and teacher organisational commitment. Principal instructional leadership had a moderate impact on teachers' organisational commitment.
Thien & Liu	Linear and nonlinear relationships between instructional leadership and teacher professional learning through teacher self-efficacy as a mediator: a partial least squares analysis	2024	Survey of 335 teachers from primary and secondary schools in Penang, Malaysia, analysed using PLS-SEM	A significant positive linear link exists between instructional leadership and teacher professional learning. This association is mediated by teachers' self-efficacy. Significant nonlinear correlations do exist.
Siriparp et al.	The effects of principal instructional leadership, collective teacher efficacy and teacher role on teacher self-efficacy: A moderated mediation examination	2022	Survey of 120 teachers, analysed using Regression Path Model	Principal instructional leadership affected teacher self-efficacy through collective teacher efficacy, which was regulated by teacher role.

<p>Awang et al., 2022</p>	<p>The influence of virtual instructional leadership on teachers' commitment: A Malaysian e-leadership case study</p>	<p>2022</p>	<p>Quantitative study using partial least squares-structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM)</p>	<p>Principals' virtual instructional leadership methods have a favourable impact on teacher dedication. Normative and ongoing commitments are unsuitable aspects for teacher commitments in the context of virtual instructional leadership.</p>
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The studies by Rahman et al., (2022) shows that the importance of experience and maturity in developing effective instructional leadership skills, which can significantly impact school management and educational outcomes. According to Amzat et al., (2022), the instructional leadership has impacts on teacher professional development. Nguyen et al., (2023) stated that instructional leadership bring positive effects on teachers' professional learning and development practices. This finding is in line with Nguyen et al., (2022) that instructional leadership practices associated with professional development and positive school climate. According to Sukarmin and Sin (2022), principal instructional leadership behavior has a significant influence on teacher commitment, with a moderate effect size. This finding is supported by Awang et al., (2022) too by stating the impact of instructional leadership on teacher's commitment. There were also scholars studied instructional leadership effect with teacher's self-efficacy such as Siriparp et al., (2022) and Thien and Liu (2024).

Leadership and School Environment

Instructional leadership has a substantial impact on school environment such as school climate, health, and the promotion of cooperation via social media, resulting in a positive and productive educational environment. A positive school climate, defined by safety, support, and academic concentration, is frequently a direct result of strong instructional leadership. Leaders set the tone by encouraging courteous relationships and focussing on academic success, which improves student and teacher engagement and overall school performance (Thapa et al., 2013). Furthermore, instructional leaders who prioritise holistic educational approaches have a significant impact on school health, which encompasses students' and staff's physical and psychological well-being. Instructional leaders play an important role in the overall well-being of their school communities by incorporating health education, supporting mental health initiatives, and maintaining a safe school environment (Basch, 2010). Furthermore, using social media to facilitate cooperation has emerged as an innovative part of instructional leadership. Leaders who use social media platforms promote professional development, increase community participation, and improve communication between staff, students, and parents. This digital strategy contributes to a more connected school community by encouraging collaborative learning and sharing best practices across larger networks (Greenhow et al., 2009). The followings are the further explanations of the subthemes.

Promoting Positive School Climate (Puruwita et al., 2022) : An essential aspect of instructional leadership is the capacity to establish and maintain a positive school environment. This entails defining clear objectives, setting high standards, and nurturing an atmosphere of respect and teamwork. A positive school climate not only enhances student academic performance but also boost teachers' morale and encourages them to stay in their roles.

Enhancing School Health (Sukri et al., 2022) : Instructional leadership has a direct impact on school health by fostering a healthy organizational culture, addressing teacher well-being, promoting effective

communication, and providing a safe and conducive learning environment. Healthy schools are better equipped to achieve educational excellence.

Fostering Collaboration through Social Media (Prasojo & Yuliana, 2021) : The use of social media by school principals for instructional leadership purposes has been shown to encourage greater collaboration among teachers and stakeholders. Social media platforms provide a way to share resources, best practices, and foster a sense of community and shared purpose. Table 4 shows the articles related to the instructional leadership and school environment.

Table 4: Summary of Instructional Leadership and School Environment

Author(s)	Title	Year	Methodology	Findings
Fred & Singh	Instructional Leadership Practices in Under-Enrolled Rural Schools in Miri, Sarawak	2021	Mixed method research using PIMRS survey and interviews	The instructional leadership level of headmasters was "medium high" across three categories. There is a significant disparity in how male and female teachers perceive headmasters' practices.
Puruwita et al.	Instructional Leadership Practices At High-Performing Vocational Schools: Administrators' Vs Teachers' Perception	2022	Survey of 155 school administrators and 336 teachers	High level of instructional leadership techniques, including creating school goals, managing instructional programs, and maintaining a pleasant school climate. Administrators and instructors have quite different perceptions.
Prasojo & Yuliana	How is social media used by Indonesian school principals for instructional leadership?	2021	Mixed methods: survey of 122 principals and interviews with 7 principals	Principals' use of social media for instructional leadership is deemed satisfactory. There is no significant difference depending on gender or age, although there is a considerable age difference for principals over 50.

Sukri et al.	School health as the mediator variable: Determinants of the principal instructional leadership behaviour	2022	Survey of 350 public primary school teachers, analysed using SEM	Principal instructional leadership behaviour had a strong direct influence on school health, which in turn affected organisational commitment, efficacy, and teacher satisfaction.
Nahdi et al.	Instructional Leadership through Curriculum Coordination: Elementary Learning Continues during COVID-19 in Indonesia	2021	Multi-coated qualitative approach using surveys and interviews	Described curriculum coordination forms prior to and after Covid-19, emphasising changes in planning, assessment, and coordination procedures. emphasised teamwork involving principals and stakeholders.

According to Fred and Singh (2021) the level of headmasters' instructional leadership in under-enrolled rural schools was rated as "medium high" based on the Principal Instructional Management Rating Scale (PIMRS). There was a statistically significant difference in the perceptions of male and female teachers regarding their headmasters' instructional leadership practices in these schools. Meanwhile Puruwita et al., (2022) demonstrated that school administrators at high-performing vocational schools exhibit high instructional leadership practices in defining school goals, managing instructional programs, and promoting a positive school climate. Also, there was a significant difference in the perceptions of instructional leadership practices between school administrators such as principals, vice-principal, head of programs and teachers in these schools. Sukri et al., (2022) stated that from their findings principal's instructional leadership behavior had a significant direct influence on school health, which in turn influenced organizational commitment, efficacy, and teacher satisfaction. Nahdi et al., (2021) finds that there is an efficient team work between instructional principals and stakeholders for enhancing the learning outcomes.

Instructional Leadership and Innovation

Instructional leadership is essential for creating innovation in schools, notably by encouraging creative teaching, incorporating information and communication technology (ICT) into the classroom, and promoting digital skills development. Instructional leaders play an important role in developing a culture that supports and promotes innovative teaching methods. Leaders may create an environment in which innovative and diverse instructional practices are not only encouraged but praised, resulting in more engaging and effective education (Hallinger & Murphy, 1985). Another area where instructional leadership is critical is in the adoption of ICT in the classroom. Leaders can help to integrate technology by providing the essential infrastructure, professional development, and strategic vision. This not only improves the teaching and learning processes, but also prepares pupils for a digitally advanced world. Effective leaders ensure that technology adoption matches with educational goals and improves learning outcomes, rather than simply functioning as an add-on (Lawless and Pellegrino, 2007). The subthemes emerged are the followings.

Encouraging Creative Teaching (Suyudi et al., 2022) : Principals who prioritize instructional leadership encourage innovative and creative teaching practices, including supporting teachers in experimenting with new teaching methods, integrating technology into the classroom, and fostering a culture of creativity and critical thinking among students.

Adopting ICT in Teaching (Mohd Siraj et al., 2023): Instructional leadership plays a crucial role in the successful implementation of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in teaching. Leaders who actively promote and support the integration of ICT help teachers in developing the necessary skills and confidence to use technology effectively, thereby enhancing the learning experience for students.

Supporting Digital Skills Development (Maisyaroh et al., 2024) : In today's digital era, educational leaders play a crucial role in developing students' digital competencies. By advocating for progressive learning and assisting educators in integrating digital resources into their curricula, principals help prepare students for future challenges and opportunities. Table 5 shows the important insights of the articles related to instructional leadership and innovation.

Table 3: Summary of Instructional Leadership and Innovation

Author(s)	Title	Year	Methodology	Findings
Suyudi et al.	The Effect of Instructional Leadership and Creative Teaching on Student Actualization: Student Satisfaction as a Mediator Variable	2022	Survey analysed using SEM	The principal's instructional leadership and unique teaching styles influence student learning satisfaction. Instructional leadership influences student self-actualization, whereas creative teaching has no direct impact unless mediated by learner satisfaction.
Maisyaroh et al.	Unveiling the nexus of leadership, culture, learning independence, passion trend-based learning, and teacher creativity in shaping digital student skills	2024	Quantitative approach using Structural Equation Modeling	Instructional leadership, organisational culture, and student learning independence have a substantial impact on passion-based learning, teacher creativity, and student skills.
Mohd Siraj et al.	The Relationship Between Principals' Leaderships Towards TVET Teachers' Motivation in Implementing ICT	2023	Correlational study using surveys, analysed with descriptive and inferential statistics	There is a significant relationship between principal leadership styles and TVET teacher motivation. Teachers' motivation to utilise ICT is influenced by both transformational and instructional leadership styles.

Suyudi et al., (2022) finds that principal's instructional leadership and creative teaching affects student learning satisfaction. Instructional leadership affects student self-actualization, while creative teaching has no direct effect unless mediated by learning satisfaction. Maisyaroh et al., (2024) demonstrated that instructional leadership significantly influenced passion-based learning, teacher creativity and student skills. Furthermore, Mohd Siraj et al., (2023) stated that instructional leadership influence teachers' motivation to integrate ICT in their classroom.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The synthesis of 16 studies on instructional leadership in ASEAN countries indicates its critical significance in improving educational results across many levels. Instructional leadership has regularly been shown to greatly improve teacher professional development, organizational commitment, and student achievement. For example, Amzat et al.'s (2022) research indicates not only the direct benefits of instructional leadership on teacher engagement, but also its long-term viability across varied cultural settings such as Indonesia and Malaysia. These findings indicate that the principles of effective instructional leadership are globally applicable, although they manifest differently in each cultural environment.

This paper contributes to the current research by doing a thorough investigation of how instructional leadership affects several aspects of the ASEAN educational system. It highlights the complicated interactions between school leadership and crucial mediating elements such as school health and collective teacher efficacy, as highlighted in the research of Siriparp et al., (2022) and Sukarmin and Sin (2021). Furthermore, it emphasizes instructional leaders' agility in embracing new technologies and tactics in response to modern issues, such as those identified by Prasojo and Yuliana (2021).

The variance in instructional leadership methods depending on demographic aspects such as gender, age, and experience, as described in research by Fred and Singh (2021) and Rahman et al. (2022), emphasises the importance of varied professional development. Tailoring training to address the various needs of school leaders can improve instructional leadership effectiveness in ASEAN countries. Finally, Suyudi et al., (2022) and Maisyaroh et al., (2024) demonstrate the significant influence of instructional leadership on student outcomes, emphasising education's goal of preparing students not only academically but also holistically to face future challenges. This connects with the broader educational objectives in the region and emphasises the transformative impact of strong school leadership.

While this study is substantial, it is limited by the availability of research that mostly focus on quantitative data. This may obscure the in-depth, qualitative findings that are critical for understanding instructional leaders' varied experiences and specific issues in the ASEAN context. Future research should use a mixed-methods approach to capture the range and depth of instructional leadership techniques. Qualitative research could delve into the personal tales of school leaders, yielding richer, context-specific insights that quantitative methods may ignore. Furthermore, longitudinal studies should be conducted to investigate the long-term influence of instructional leadership practices on educational results. To promote inclusive educational practices, researchers must also investigate the effects of instructional leadership on marginalised groups inside schools.

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